

Quality of Life in Patients with Gonarthrosis Undergoing Conservative Treatment at UMF 35

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To examine the quality of life of patients with gonarthrosis who underwent conservative treatment. **Methods:** A descriptive, prospective, observational, and cross-sectional study was conducted with a sample of 114 patients registered at Family Medicine Unit 35, calculated using the formula for finite populations. A non-probability sampling method was used. The Oxford Knee Quality of Life Scale was administered. Statistical analysis included chi-square tests. **Results:** A significant difference ($p < 0.001$, chi-square) was found in quality of life. Those receiving conservative treatment (weight control), those receiving conservative treatment (physical exercise), and those without pharmacological treatment were more frequently associated with excellent and good quality of life. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrated that conservative treatment (weight control and physical exercise), as well as those without pharmacological treatment, is associated with a better perception of quality of life in this study group, particularly through weight control and physical exercise.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over time, focusing on the particularities of the Mexican population, the activities that are carried out and the risk factors, joint diseases have experienced an increase.

This research focused on analyzing the quality of life of patients with gonarthrosis, in individuals aged 50 to 65 years; Primarily aimed at the family doctor, who has the ability to identify early all people with gonarthrosis, who could experience a significant improvement if they undergo conservative treatment in a timely manner.

Among the benefits of this research protocol is the reduction of costs, since conservative treatment represents a lower long-term economic impact for the health institution, as it would prevent the population from having to undergo more expensive surgical treatments.

In the long term, new knowledge will emerge about alternative therapies, which, although already documented in the literature, were not used correctly, because the necessary importance is not given to primary medicine as it should be.

II. METHODS

A descriptive, observational, prospective and cross-sectional study was carried out in the Family Medicine Unit No. 35 "Zaragoza" of the IMSS, located in Iztacalco, Mexico City, during the year 2024. The study population consisted of

114 beneficiary patients with a diagnosis of gonarthrosis, aged between 50 and 65 years, undergoing conservative treatment provided by the family doctor.

The sample size was determined using the formula for finite populations, adjusted for losses, based on a universe of 290 patients with gonarthrosis registered in ARIMAC in 2023. Sampling was non-probabilistic, convenience, and consecutive. Patients with gonarthrosis, with or without comorbidities, who agreed to participate by providing informed consent, which was explained in detail and signed voluntarily, were included. Patients with other knee pathologies, candidates for surgery, those with a psychiatric history, or those who declined to participate were excluded.

The protocol was approved by the Local Ethics and Research Committee in Health (CLIEIS 3509). The Oxford Knee Quality of Life Scale, an internationally validated ordinal instrument, was used, with the following cut-off points: >41 (excellent), 34-41 (good), 27-33 (moderate), and <27 (poor). This instrument has demonstrated high reliability and is applicable to the Latin American population. The Kellgren and Lawrence scale, standardized for severity levels, was used to diagnose gonarthrosis.

Data collection was carried out through a structured interview in an outpatient setting, accompanied by direct questioning and review of the digital medical record.

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Variables such as age, sex, body mass index (BMI), risk factors (obesity, sedentary lifestyle, comorbidities), and type of conservative treatment (weight control, physical exercise, medications) were collected.

The statistical analysis was descriptive and inferential. Frequencies, percentages, measures of central tendency (mean, median, mode), and measures of dispersion (standard deviation, variance, range) were calculated. For bivariate analysis between categorical variables, the Chi-square test was applied, establishing statistical significance with $p < 0.05$.

The study made it possible to identify the quality of life in relation to the different types of conservative treatment for gonarthrosis and the risk factors present, based on standardized clinical guidelines and parameters defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) and current clinical standards.

III. RESULTS

A total of 114 patients were included, the average age was 57.89 years, with a higher percentage of men than women.

Regarding Body Mass Index, the average BMI of the total sample was found to be 28.245, with a standard deviation of 3.87 (minimum 20.6, maximum 36.4). A significant difference ($p < 0.001$, chi-square test) was found in quality of life (QoL) according to BMI classification, with individuals with normal BMI and overweight more frequently associated with excellent and good QoL, and those with grade I obesity with moderate and poor QoL.

Regarding the degree of gonarthrosis, obtained from digital clinical records, it was found that the mild and moderate types have a higher frequency in the total sample.

Chart 1. Quality of Life Classification * Conservative Treatment: Weight Control

In this sample, a significant difference $p < 0.001$ (chi square) was found in the QoL, with people with weight control being more frequently associated with excellent and good QoL.

Chart 2. Quality of Life Classification * Conservative Treatment: Physical Exercise.

In this sample, a significant difference $p < 0.001$ (chi square) was found in the QoL, with physical exercise being more frequently associated with excellent and good QoL in people with TC.

Chart 3. Quality of Life Classification * Conservative Treatment: Pharmacological

In this sample, a significant difference $p < 0.001$ (chi square) was found in the CV, with people without Pharmacological CT being more frequently associated with excellent and good CV.

Regarding the established risk factors, it is observed that in the total population studied there is a higher frequency of obesity and sedentary lifestyle.

IV. DISCUSSION

The most frequent site of osteoarthritis is the knee, a chronic, degenerative, and progressive joint disease that affects 240 per 100,000 individuals annually. Eighty percent of patients experience limitations in their mobility, and 25% are unable to perform daily activities. These disabilities are primarily linked to pain and manifest as difficulties walking, climbing stairs, performing household chores, or standing upright. These changes result in a decreased quality of life and a considerable psychological impact. (36)

In Mexico, it is one of the most significant causes of disability after the age of 40, where 80% of individuals over 65 years of age present radiological alterations that indicate arthropathy. (37)

Several factors explain the prevalence of this joint pathology in women, such as obesity and joint laxity. Obesity is a significant risk factor for the development of knee osteoarthritis, frequently reported in most studies, and affects not only the onset of the disease but also the response to treatment (38). This was observed in the results of this study, where weight control was a key factor in achieving excellent and good quality of life. Similarly, our study concluded that the majority of the sample with this disease was male, although some risk factors, such as obesity and sedentary lifestyle, remained constant across the majority of the studied population.

Luis Espejo Antúnez, María Ángeles Cerdero Duran, Berta Caro Puertolas, and Guillermo Téllez de Peralta conducted a study on the effects of physical exercise and quality of life in elderly, institutionalized patients diagnosed with gonarthrosis. In this study, they used the Spanish version of the SF-36 Health Survey to measure quality of life, with a total sample of 45 participants. They concluded that controlled physical exercise yielded positive results in both functional aspects, such as pain, stiffness, and physical function, as well as psychological aspects. However, they determined that the SF-36 questionnaire was not suitable for validating quality of life in these patients. Nevertheless, based on these authors' conclusions, our results using the Oxford Knee Quality of Life Scale, an instrument that comprehensively studies the quality of life of patients with gonarthrosis, yielded similar results, indicating that conservative treatment based on physical exercise was associated with excellent and good quality of life.

It is for all these reasons that it is highlighted that the quality of life in patients with gonarthrosis is benefited by the start of conservative treatment, mainly based on 2 major pillars which are weight control and physical exercise, providing a series of benefits, among which are mentioned the synergy of physical exercise for weight control, improvement of flexibility, stability and joint mobility, increased capacity and resistance to work, reduction of edema and pain, as well as a decrease in the need for recurrent drugs in this joint pathology(39), resulting in an excellent and good quality of life, supporting our hypothesis.

V. CONCLUSIONS

It was shown that conservative treatment (weight control and physical exercise), as well as those that do not require pharmacological treatment, is associated with a better perception of quality of life in this study group through weight control and physical exercise.

It is essential to implement a comprehensive prevention and monitoring program at the primary care level; this strategy would help reduce the progression of the disease,

improve patient functionality, and avoid more invasive and costly surgical procedures in the long term.

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